

Table S5 Magmatic activities from Cambrian to late Carboniferous occurred in the Mazongshan unit, Hongliuhe-Niujuanzi-Yueyashan suture and Huaniushan microcontinent

Tectonic units	Samples names	Lithology	Aga (Ma)	error	References	References No.
Huaniushan microcontinent	GHSN-01	gabbro dyke	356	1	Xie et al. (2012)	1
Huaniushan microcontinent	GHSN-02	olivine gabbro-norite	367	1	Xie et al. (2012)	1
Huaniushan microcontinent	GHCN-01	olivine gabbro-norite	358	5	Xie et al. (2012)	1
Huaniushan microcontinent	GHCN-02	gabbro dyke	357	4	Xie et al. (2012)	1
Huaniushan microcontinent	GQ01-21	Pantuoshan monzonite	422	2	Ding et al. (2015)	2
Huaniushan microcontinent	GQ02-17	Pantuoshan monzonite	417	2	Ding et al. (2015)	2
Huaniushan microcontinent	YZHS02-21	Yingzuishan monzonite	424	1	Ding et al. (2015)	2
Huaniushan microcontinent	08NC05	tonalite gneiss	468	4	Cleven et al. (2018)	3
Huaniushan microcontinent	09DDS45-1	rhyolites	368	3	Guo et al. (2014)	4
Huaniushan microcontinent	09DDS41-1	syenoporphyries	371	1	Guo et al. (2014)	4
Huaniushan microcontinent	LYB19-2	Biotite gneissic granite	424	4	Mao et al. (2010)	5
Huaniushan microcontinent	08LY02	Nb-enriched basalts	452	4	Mao et al. (2012)	6
Huaniushan microcontinent	08LY01	dacite	442	3	Mao et al. (2012)	6
Huaniushan microcontinent	LYB19	adakite	424	3	Mao et al. (2012)	6
Huaniushan microcontinent	08L05	adakite	374	3	Mao et al. (2012)	6
Huaniushan microcontinent	131042	tonalite	433	3	Yu et al. (2016)	7
Huaniushan microcontinent	131043	tonalite	434	4	Yu et al. (2016)	7
Huaniushan microcontinent	141068	tonalite	360	3	Yu et al. (2016)	7
Huaniushan microcontinent	141071	tonalite	370	3	Yu et al. (2016)	7
Huaniushan microcontinent	132104	volcaniclastic rock	391	3	Yu et al. (2016)	7
Huaniushan microcontinent	132039	porphyritic monzogranite	398	4	Yu et al. (2016)	7
Huaniushan microcontinent	LY-22	gabbro	404	14	Wang et al. (2016)	8
Huaniushan microcontinent	LY-65	mylonitized diorite	466	7	Wang et al. (2016)	8
Huaniushan microcontinent	LY-69	granite	451	6	Wang et al. (2016)	8
Huaniushan microcontinent	LY-94	granite	422	5	Wang et al. (2016)	8
Huaniushan microcontinent	LY-101	granite	445	4	Wang et al. (2016)	8
Huaniushan microcontinent	XJ11-139	gabbro	443	1	Li et al. (2015)	9
Huaniushan microcontinent	XJ11-137	granite	436	2	Li et al. (2015)	9
Huaniushan microcontinent	XJ11-140	diorite	437	2	Li et al. (2015)	9
Huaniushan microcontinent	XJ11-150	gabbro-diorite	449	1	Li et al. (2015)	9
Huaniushan microcontinent	LY-2-27/61	K-feldspar granite	436	9	Zhao et al. (2007)	10
Huaniushan microcontinent	LY-12-17	granodiorite	423	8	Zhao et al. (2007)	10
Huaniushan microcontinent	LY-2-55/LY-6-18	monzonitic granite	397	7	Zhao et al. (2007)	10
Huaniushan microcontinent	HTS-1	syenogranite	419	4	Zhu et al. (2016)	11
Huaniushan microcontinent	SJP-3r	Biotite monzogranite	404	2	Zhu et al. (2016)	11
Huaniushan microcontinent	XIMZ158	Haergen two-mica granite	409	3	Wang et al. (2017)	12
Huaniushan microcontinent	SF07	granite	415	3	Li et al. (2009)	13
Huaniushan microcontinent	B70823-8	K-feldspar granite	397	3	Li et al. (2011a)	14
Huaniushan microcontinent	16BS005	K-feldspar granite	399	2	This study	
Huaniushan microcontinent	16BS123	K-feldspar granite	410	2	This study	
Huaniushan microcontinent	16BS124	K-feldspar granite	406	2	This study	

Huanishan microcontinent	16BS125	K-feldspar granite	411	3	This study	
Yueyashan suture	08YYS01	plagiogranite	533	2	Ao et al. (2011)	25
Yueyashan suture	HBS5309	plagiogranites	536	7	Hou et al. (2012)	26
Niujuanzi ophiolite	NJ-1A	plagiogranites	430	2	Wang et al. (2018)	27
Niujuanzi ophiolite	NJ-18A	plagiogranites	449	2	Wang et al. (2018)	27
Niujuanzi ophiolite	NJ-26A	gabbro	354 ^a	3	Wang et al. (2018)	27
Niujuanzi ophiolite	NJ-28A	diabase	433	3	Wang et al. (2018)	27
Niujuanzi ophiolite	NJ-45A	gabbro	434	3	Wang et al. (2018)	27
Yueyashan suture	P2TW2	metagabbro	542	1	Hu et al. (2015)	24
Yueyashan suture	P2TW1	gabbro	527	1	Hu et al. (2015)	24
Yueyashan suture	TW37	gabbro-diorite	530	5	Hu et al. (2015)	24
Yueyashan suture	P1TW2	plagiogranites	530	1	Hu et al. (2015)	24
Hongliuhe suture	HLH-124	gabbro	520	6	Cleven et al. (2015)	28
Xichangjing suture	XCJ04-3	pegmatoid gabbro	535	6	Shi et al. (2018)	29
Yushishan suture	YYSS02-2	gabbro	521	4	Shi et al. (2018)	29
Hongliuhe suture	HLH14-1	gabbro	528	3	Shi et al. (2018)	29
Hongliuhe suture	10Tzh63	plagiogranite	444	2	Tian et al. (2014)	30
Huoshishan suture	HSS02	gabbro	411	4	Tian et al. (2014)	30
Huoshishan suture	10Tzh64	basalt	435	2	Tian et al. (2014)	30
Mazongshan unit	16BS117	K-feldspar granite	403	2	This study	
Mazongshan unit	16BS119	granites	405	4	This study	
Mazongshan unit	16BS118	granites	400	2	This study	
Mazongshan unit	XIMZ134	Baitoushan muscovite granite	409	3	Wang et al. (2017)	12
Mazongshan unit	XIMZ141	Baitoushan muscovite granite	395	4	Wang et al. (2017)	12
Mazongshan Unit	BS07-136	post-collisional granite	402	3	Zheng et al. (2012)	15
Mazongshan Unit	10ASJ10	gneissic diorite	424	3	Ao et al. (2016)	16
Mazongshan Unit	11SBJ50	gneissic granite	450	4	Song et al. (2013b)	17
Mazongshan Unit	11SBJ55	mylonitic orthogneiss	457	5	Song et al. (2013b)	17
Mazongshan Unit	11SBJ66	migmatitic gneiss	452	11	Song et al. (2013b)	17
Mazongshan Unit	11SBJ02	foliated granite	349	5	Song et al. (2013b)	17
Mazongshan Unit	11CH23	mylonitic granite	410	5	Song et al. (2013b)	17
Mazongshan Unit	11CH05	granitic gneiss	526	6	Song et al. (2013b)	17
Mazongshan Unit	10SYQ03	granitic gneiss	471	8	Song et al. (2013a)	18
Mazongshan Unit	10SYQ05	granitic gneiss	448	4	Song et al. (2013a)	18
Mazongshan Unit	10SYQ07	augen gneiss	463	7	Song et al. (2013a)	18
Mazongshan Unit	10SYQ08	mylonitic granite	474	10	Song et al. (2013a)	18
Mazongshan Unit	10MZS04	biotite-plagioclase gneiss	374	3	Song et al. (2013a)	18
Mazongshan Unit	11SJZ16	biotite-plagioclase gneiss	397	3	Song et al. (2015)	19
Mazongshan Unit	11LBQ33	gabbroic-diorite	442	2	Song et al. (2015)	19
Mazongshan Unit	12LBQ64	porphyritic granite	434	2	Song et al. (2015)	19
Mazongshan Unit	12LBQ07	mylonitic granite	398	3	Song et al. (2015)	19
Mazongshan Unit	12LBQ32	granitic gneiss	464	2	Song et al. (2015)	19
Mazongshan Unit	12LBQ16	mylonitic granite	401	4	Song et al. (2015)	19
Mazongshan Unit	12CH17	gneissic monzo-diorite	420	3	Song et al. (2015)	19

Mazongshan Unit	X10-48-1	mylonitized granite	446	3	Yuan et al. (2018)	20
Mazongshan Unit	X10-49-1	mylonitized granite	444	3	Yuan et al. (2018)	20
Mazongshan Unit	X10-50-1	mylonitized granite	443	2	Yuan et al. (2018)	20
Mazongshan Unit	X10-51-1	mylonitized granite	434	2	Yuan et al. (2018)	20
Mazongshan Unit	X10-52-1	mylonitized granite	430	2	Yuan et al. (2018)	20
Mazongshan Unit	X10-54-1	mylonitized granite	438	4	Yuan et al. (2018)	20
Mazongshan unit	BS07-111	diorite	426	3	Zhang et al. (2018)	21
Mazongshan unit	AB10-80	mylonitic Monzogranite	408	3	Zhang et al. (2018)	21
Mazongshan unit	AB10-100	biotite Granodiorite	365	2	Zhang et al. (2018)	21
Mazongshan unit	BA11-87	quartz diorite	435	2	Zheng et al. (2018)	22
Mazongshan unit	BA11-91	quartz monzonite	421	2	Zheng et al. (2018)	22
Mazongshan unit	BA11-96	K-feldspar granite	401	2	Zheng et al. (2018)	22
Mazongshan unit	BA11-118	granodiorite	434	6	Zheng et al. (2018)	22
Mazongshan unit	BA11-130	leucogranite	402	1	Zheng et al. (2018)	22
Mazongshan Unit	W08-295	Dongqiyishan granite	356	2	Zhang et al. (2012a)	23
Mazongshan unit	TW7	andesite	521	15	Hu et al. (2015)	24
Mazongshan unit	P7TW2	granodiorite	442	2	Hu et al. (2015)	24
Mazongshan unit	BS17-3	basalt	411	3	Zheng et al. (2019)	31
Mazongshan unit	BS19-1	andesite	428	4	Zheng et al. (2019)	31
Mazongshan unit	BA11-62	andesite	415	3	Zheng et al. (2019)	31
Mazongshan unit	BA11-60	andesite	421	4	Zheng et al. (2019)	31
Mazongshan unit	BS44-1	andesite	431	4	Zheng et al. (2019)	31
Mazongshan unit	BS20-4	basalt	434	5	Zheng et al. (2019)	31

Note: a means that sample NJ-26A has two age clusters and the 354 Ma may represent the metamorphic ages.

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